

Machine Learning for Predicting the Mechanical Properties of Composite Materials: A Comparison of Ensemble Methods and Analytical Models

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Abstract

This study examines how machine learning (ML) models can predict the mechanical characteristics of glass fiber-reinforced polymers (GFRPs), focusing on the axial Young's modulus (E_{11}), Poisson's ratio (ν_{12}), and in-plane shear modulus (G_{12}). Several ML algorithms, such as CatBoost, XGBoost, and Gradient Boosting ensemble methods, were compared with traditional analytical models and Digimat-simulated data. The findings showed that ML models, especially ensemble methods, achieved higher accuracy, with R^2 values above 0.997 and errors typically under 3% for E_{11} and 5% for G_{12} . Critical features affecting these properties—like fiber volume fraction, matrix Poisson's ratio, and shear modulus—were identified. Sensitivity analysis revealed fiber volume fraction as the most influential for E_{11} , while matrix properties significantly impacted ν_{12} and G_{12} . The study also points out that simpler models such as k-NN and SVR cannot capture complex feature interactions. Overall, the results suggest that ML approaches are promising for predicting material properties and optimizing composite design. Future research will aim to validate these models with larger, more varied datasets and explore hybrid techniques for further enhancement.

Keywords: *Glass fiber-reinforced polymers (GFRPs), Machine Learning, Ensembled models, Mechanical Properties.*

Introduction

Glass fiber-reinforced polymers (GFRPs) are among the most widely used composite materials in modern engineering owing to their excellent strength-to-weight ratio, durability, corrosion resistance, and design flexibility (Mardanshahi, et al., 2020; Rautela, & Gopalakrishnan, 2021). Their properties make them indispensable in diverse industrial sectors, including aerospace, automotive, marine, and civil engineering, where structural stability, lightweight design, and long-term performance are critical (Pelín, & Pelín, 2024; Cao, et al., 2024). In aerospace and aeronautics, GFRPs—particularly high-strength variants such as S-glass—are applied in structural panels, cargo liners, protective armor, and stealth technology due to their superior modulus, fatigue resistance, and non-conductive properties (Krishna, et al., 2016). In

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construction, their dimensional stability, impact resistance, and corrosion resistance make them suitable for architectural panels, skylights, and reinforcement systems, while chemical plants, sewage systems, and pollution control devices benefit from their ability to withstand harsh environments (Li, E. et al., 2013). Applications extend further into the automotive and railway industries, where GFRPs replace heavier materials to improve fuel efficiency, safety, and durability in structural components (Yasufuku, S. (1994), as well as in marine, medical, and consumer products, where toughness, stability, and resistance to degradation are required (Siengchin, et al., 2022; Rajamahendran, et al., 2021; Rajak, et al., 2019).

The exceptional versatility of GFRPs stems from the interplay of factors such as fiber type (A-glass, C-glass, E-glass, or S-glass), fiber orientation, volume fraction, fiber–matrix interaction, and the chosen manufacturing process (Soutis, 2005). While these variables enable precise tailoring of composite performance, they also introduce complexity in predicting mechanical behavior. Conventional experimental techniques, such as tensile, flexural, fatigue, and impact tests, remain the benchmark for performance evaluation; however, they are costly, time-consuming, and often require large amounts of material (Liu, et al., 2014). Numerical simulations and analytical models have been explored as alternatives; however, they are computationally demanding and frequently lack generalizability across different composite configurations (Kaddour, et al., 2013).

In this context, machine learning (ML) has emerged as a powerful tool in materials science, capable of detecting complex, nonlinear relationships between input parameters and mechanical properties. Algorithms, such as artificial neural networks (ANNs), support vector machines (SVMs), decision trees, and random forests, have been successfully applied to predict the tensile strength, Young’s modulus, impact resistance, and fatigue life of fiber-reinforced composites (Bhadeshia, 1999). More advanced frameworks, such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and recurrent neural networks (RNNs), have demonstrated strong performance in tasks such as failure prediction, stress–strain modeling, and fatigue resistance assessment (Arun Prakash, et al., 2022; Wang, et al., 2022). Hybrid approaches that integrate ML with physics-based simulations, such as finite element analysis (FEA), further enhance predictive reliability by combining data-driven insights with established mechanical theory (Wang, et al., 2015; Tsai, Huang, & Chang, 2023).

However, the effectiveness of ML-driven models heavily depends on the availability and quality of training datasets. Integrating experimental data from scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), and mechanical tests (tensile, compression, and impact) has significantly improved model robustness (Lee, et al., 2024). For instance, ensemble methods that combine ANNs, SVMs, and decision trees have achieved prediction accuracies exceeding 95% when applied to GFRP composite datasets with varying orientations, fiber contents, and curing conditions (Wang, Zhao, & Li, 2023). Hybrid ML-FEA frameworks have demonstrated superior generalizability when validated against experimental benchmarks (Nguyen, et al., 2024). Optimization techniques, such as genetic algorithms, particle swarm optimization (PSO), and reinforcement learning, are being explored to fine-tune process parameters, enabling the discovery of novel composite formulations with enhanced strength, durability, and impact resistance (Xu, Lui & Chen, 2022; Jiao, & Zhao, 2019).

Advances in this area notwithstanding, systematic studies utilizing robust machine learning models to forecast and fine-tune the mechanical properties of GFRPs are still somewhat restricted, especially when taking into account various material formulations and production settings. This study develops and assesses machine learning models for forecasting the mechanical properties of glass fibre reinforced polymers. This study seeks to improve predictive precision, decrease dependence on extensive testing, and offer significant insights into material design and performance refinement for high-priority engineering applications by combining experimental data with sophisticated machine learning techniques.

Methodology

This section outlines the systematic approach adopted to predict the mechanical properties of GFRPs using synthetic datasets generated using ML and MSH techniques. The methodology is structured into four main stages: dataset generation, preprocessing and feature selection, ML model development, and model evaluation.

Dataset Generation

Synthetic data generation using Digimat MF

Synthetic data generated via Digimat MF were used instead of relying only on experimental datasets. The experimental characterization of GFRPs across different fiber types, orientations, and volume fractions is costly, time-consuming, and often results in limited sample sizes, while machine learning needs large and diverse datasets for effective training. Digimat MF, based on the validated Mori–Tanaka mean-field homogenization scheme, provides physically consistent predictions of composite behavior and enables the systematic exploration of the design space beyond what is feasible experimentally. Synthetic datasets enable balanced sampling and controlled variability, reducing bias and enhancing model generalization. This approach combines computational efficiency with physical accuracy to create a scalable basis for future experimental validation.

The range of input parameters was selected to reflect values commonly reported in engineering practice, ensuring a broad coverage of realistic material systems. The effective properties are calculated from the constituent elastic moduli, Poisson’s ratios, densities, aspect ratios, and fiber–matrix interfacial characteristics. Table 1 summarizes the ranges of glass fibers and epoxy resins.

Table 1. Dataset Parameters of the GFRP Composites

Materials	Mechanical properties	Ranges from -- to	Units
Glass fiber	Young modulus	70000 to 100000	MPa
	Poisson’s ratio	0.20–0.30	-
	Fiber friction	0.3 to 0.5	-
	Density	2.5 to 2.6	g/cm ³
	Aspect ratio	10–100	mm
Resin (epoxy)	Young modulus	2000–5000	MPa
	Poisson’s ratio	0.3 to 0.4	-
	Density	1.1 to 1.4	g/cm ³

The effective mechanical properties obtained included axial Young’s modulus (E_{11}), in-plane Poisson’s ratio (ν_{12}), and in-plane shear modulus (G_{12}). These were computed from the stress–strain responses as follows:

$$E_{11} = \frac{\sigma_{11}}{\varepsilon_{11}} \quad (1)$$

$$\nu_{12} = \frac{\varepsilon_{22}}{\varepsilon_{11}} \quad (2)$$

$$G_{12} = \frac{\tau_{12}}{\gamma_{12}} \quad (3)$$

where, σ_{11} and ε_{11} is the stress and strain in the fiber direction, τ_{12} and γ_{12} is the shear stress and strain in the 1-2 plane.

Table 2 shows a subset of the generated dataset that includes the computed values of these mechanical properties for specific combinations of input parameters.

Table 2 Sample Dataset Generated Using Digimat MF Software

Fiber's Young Modulus	Fiber Poisson's Ratio	Fiber Friction	Fiber aspect ratio (L/D)	Resin Youngs Modulus	Resin Poisson's Ratio	E_{11}	ν_{12}	G_{12}
85481	0.27	0.38	12	2408	0.39	20482	0.53468	1710.7
86431	0.35	0.17	58	3344	0.31	16740	0.39947	1656.7
85318	0.34	0.41	92	2292	0.32	35482	0.42255	1755.8
79166	0.23	0.38	71	3999	0.29	31965	0.36523	2852.7
81147	0.26	0.1	14	2907	0.25	7717.6	0.29451	1346.5

Data Preprocessing

The dataset comprised 1,000 entries generated using the Digimat-MF homogenization tool to simulate the mechanical response of glass fiber/epoxy composites. Input variables included: (i) fiber volume fraction (10%–100%), (ii) fiber orientation angle, (iii) constituent properties (fiber/matrix stiffness, strength, and Poisson's ratio), and (iv) processing conditions (temperature and pressure). The target outputs were the axial Young's modulus (E_{11}), Poisson's ratio (ν_{12}), and in-plane shear modulus (G_{12}).

The preprocessing steps involved normalization to [0,1], correlation-based feature screening, and an 80:20 train-test split. Ten regression algorithms were implemented: linear regression, elastic net, k-nearest neighbors (k-NN), support vector regression (SVR), decision tree, random forest, GBM, XGBoost, CatBoost, and AdaBoost. An ensemble model combining high-performing learners was also developed. The hyperparameters were optimized using grid search cross-validation. The model performance was assessed using R^2 , RMSE, MAE, and MSE.

Machine Learning Models

Figure 1. Machine Learning Models under Study

Ten ML regression models were applied to predict the mechanical properties of the composite materials, and the results were compared and analyzed. It involved data preprocessing, feature selection, model

training, and evaluation in a systematic methodology. The methodology diagram (Figure 1) illustrates the above process: a prepared dataset is preprocessed, split into training and testing subsets, and various ML models are trained and evaluated on the training set before being evaluated on the testing set. An ensemble approach is then applied to increase the predictive accuracy using the strengths of the best-performing models. The models used include Random Forest (RF), Gradient Boosting (GB), XGBoost (XGB), k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), Elastic Net Regression (EN), Linear Regression (LR), Decision Tree (DT), CatBoost, AdaBoost, and Support Vector Regression (SVR).

The dataset is applied to various ML regression models. The best performing models are selected after training and evaluation. These models are combined into an ensemble to exploit their strengths and alleviate their weaknesses. In this step, the goal is to integrate several models to improve prediction accuracy and robustness. The mechanical properties of composite materials are predicted with the ensemble model (Rothenhäusler, et al., 2025). The validity and effectiveness of such a prediction are validated using the test data.

Training and Validation of the Strategy

The ML models were trained using the 80% training subset and evaluated against the 20% testing subset. A 10-fold cross-validation was used to reduce the bias associated with a single partition. The training data were divided into ten folds, with nine folds used for training and one for validation in each iteration. The procedure was repeated ten times, and the results were reported.

Evaluation Metrics

Model performance was quantified using the following standard regression metrics:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum(y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (4)$$

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (5)$$

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (6)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (7)$$

where y_i and \hat{y}_i are the experimental and predicted values, respectively, and \bar{y} is the mean of the observed values.

Results

Model Performance

Axial Young's Modulus (E_{11})

The performance metrics for predicting E_{11} are summarized in Table 3. The ensemble model achieved the best results ($R^2 = 0.997$, $RMSE = 581$), outperforming all single learners. Among the individual models, the boosting-based approaches (CatBoost, XGBoost, and GBM) consistently reached $R^2 > 0.994$, whereas linear regression and decision trees performed moderately. Simpler models such as k-NN and SVR showed poor generalization, with R^2 values < 0.3 and negative, respectively. The results imply that these models find it difficult to deal with the complexity of the dataset. Elastic Net and Linear Regression perform workably but not predictively accurately as compared to boosting-based models (Figure 2 in Appendix).

Table 3. Performance Metrics for Predicting E_{11} Using Various Models

Model	R ²	MSE	MAE	RMSE
Random Forest	0.989096	1.279169e+06	784.286504	1131.003405
Gradient Boosting	0.994196	6.808886e+05	615.163410	825.159744
XGBoost	0.994893	5.991373e+05	565.020895	774.039618
Catboost	0.995568	5.198933e+05	565.942841	721.036242
k-NN	0.273371	8.524438e+07	6292.489247	9232.788106
Elastic Net	0.851817	1.738413e+07	3516.757203	4169.427940
Linear Regression	0.974739	2.963481e+06	1281.372521	1721.476330
Decision Tree	0.967214	3.846233e+06	1317.426389	1961.181532
SVR	-0.006513	1.180791e+08	9192.548962	10866.418783
AdaBoost	0.933071	7.851736e+06	2293.078639	2802.094869
Ensemble	0.997125	3.372986e+05	471.121200	580.774171

Poisson’s Ratio (ν_{12})

Results in Table 4 confirm similar trends. The ensemble again yielded the highest predictive accuracy (R² = 0.997, RMSE = 0.0047). Boosting methods produced highly reliable results (R² ≈ 0.996), while random forest, linear regression, and decision trees performed acceptably. The elastic net, k-NN, and SVR were ineffective, with R² near zero or negative (Figure 3 in Appendix).

Table 4. Performance of the Models in Predicting Poisson’s Ratio (ν)

Model	R ²	MSE	MAE	RMSE
Random Forest	0.991602	0.000063	0.004252	0.007911
Gradient Boosting	0.996756	0.000024	0.002536	0.004916
XGBoost	0.996056	0.000029	0.002440	0.005421
CatBoost	0.996870	0.000023	0.002259	0.004829
k-NN	0.148484	0.006345	0.057727	0.079658
Elastic Net	-0.001655	0.007464	0.074816	0.086396
Linear Regression	0.984819	0.000113	0.008377	0.010636
Decision Tree	0.987310	0.000095	0.005058	0.009725
SVR	0.003404	0.007427	0.074672	0.086177
AdaBoost	0.979503	0.000153	0.009579	0.012359
Ensemble	0.997063	0.000022	0.002177	0.004678

In-Plane Shear Modulus (G_{12})

For G_{12} (Table 5), the ensemble achieved R² = 0.998 and RMSE = 32.3, followed by CatBoost (R² = 0.997). Boosting approaches generally provided accurate predictions, while simpler regressors again underperformed.

Overall, ensemble and boosting-based models consistently delivered superior performance across all mechanical properties, with k-NN and SVR being unsuitable for the composite dataset’s complex, nonlinear feature space (Figure 4 in Appendix).

Table 5. Performance of the Models for Predicting In-Plane Shear Modulus (G)

Model	R ²	MSE	MAE	RMSE
Random Forest	0.991847	4247.045733	47.715004	65.169362
Gradient Boosting	0.995303	2446.889522	32.875764	49.466044
XGBoost	0.995789	2193.467064	30.340964	46.834464
CatBoost	0.997264	1425.380828	27.146360	37.754216
k-NN	0.612202	202012.581603	305.460312	449.458098
Elastic Net	0.895893	54231.483239	174.961111	232.876541
Linear Regression	0.964073	18715.257719	108.290058	136.803720
Decision Tree	0.981143	9823.267031	72.445408	99.112396
SVR	-0.013419	527912.665063	581.805072	726.575987
AdaBoost	0.954971	23456.817893	128.435949	153.156188
Ensemble	0.998000	1041.677683	21.858545	32.275032

Cross-validation

k-fold cross-validation (k = 10) was employed to assess the reliability and robustness of the machine learning models. The dataset was divided into 10 equal subsets, with 9 used for training and 1 for testing, and the process was repeated for each fold (Tables 6–8). This approach mitigates overfitting and provides a more comprehensive evaluation of model performance across different data segments. Performance metrics, including R², mean squared error (MSE), mean absolute error (MAE), and root mean squared error (RMSE) were calculated for each fold. For E₁₁, most folds achieved R² > 0.995, with lower performance in Fold 3 (R² = 0.961) and Fold 9 (R² = 0.917). ν₁₂ predictions were highly stable across all folds, with RMSE values on the order of 10⁻³. G₁₂ predictions were consistently robust (average R² = 0.996).

$$CV\ Score = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K CV_k \tag{8}$$

Table 6. Summary of the Fold-Wise Results of the Prediction of Mechanical Properties, Namely, Axial Young’s Modulus (E)

Fold no#	R ²	MSE	MAE	RMSE
Fold 1	0.996	295569.8	417.56	543.66
Fold 2	0.997	312822.5	455.19	559.30
Fold 3	0.961	3781293.7	559.07	1944.55
Fold 4	0.997	317361.0	459.89	563.34
Fold 5	0.995	394254.3	464.12	627.89
Fold 6	0.994	522328.6	439.42	722.72
Fold 7	0.996	342286.1	431.54	585.05
Fold 8	0.998	172478.3	324.20	415.30
Fold 9	0.917	7340874.1	600.67	2709.40
Fold 10	0.998	195278.8	317.26	441.90

Table 7. Summary of the Fold-Wise Results of the Prediction of Mechanical Properties, Namely, Poisson Ratio (ν)

Fold no#	R ²	MSE	MAE	RMSE
Fold 1	0.997	1.718	0.0021	0.0041
Fold 2	0.998	1.164	0.0018	0.0034

Fold 3	0.968	0.002	0.0032	0.0151
Fold 4	0.997	1.930	0.0025	0.0043
Fold 5	0.997	1.532	0.0024	0.0039
Fold 6	0.999	5.797	0.0017	0.0024
Fold 7	0.998	1.275	0.0017	0.0035
Fold 8	0.999	3.586	0.0012	0.0018
Fold 9	0.999	2.496	0.00113	0.0015
Fold 10	0.999	3.251	0.00122	0.0018

Table 8 Summary of the Fold-Wise Results of the Mechanical Properties Prediction, Namely, In-Plane Shear Modulus (G)

Fold no#	R ²	MSE	MAE	RMSE
Fold 1	0.997	1008.95	19.794	31.764
Fold 2	0.998	859.54	20.594	29.317
Fold 3	0.995	2355.40	22.601	48.532
Fold 4	0.998	774.69	20.681	27.833
Fold 5	0.996	1784.96	24.723	42.248
Fold 6	0.998	866.90	23.166	29.443
Fold 7	0.998	705.83	19.322	26.567
Fold 8	0.999	432.55	16.689	20.798
Fold 9	0.999	391.01	14.743	19.773
Fold 10:	0.999	235.71	12.106	15.352

Figure 2. Graphical Presentation of Cross-Validation Actual vs Predicted (a) E, (b) ν , and (c) G

Discussion

The results demonstrate that machine learning provides a robust and accurate framework for predicting the mechanical properties of GFRPs. Ensemble-based models, particularly gradient boosting and its variants, consistently outperformed simpler algorithms such as k-Nearest Neighbors and SVR. This superior performance can be attributed to the ability of tree-based ensembles to capture nonlinear feature interactions, thereby accounting for complex relationships between variables. Furthermore, the iterative process of adaptive weighting mechanisms enables these models to minimize error and refine their predictions over time. Consequently, ensemble-based models have emerged as the preferred choice for predicting the mechanical properties of GFRPs.

Feature importance analysis confirmed the physical plausibility of the models (Table 16). The results showed a clear and logical correlation between the models' performance and the underlying material properties. Specifically, fiber volume fraction emerged as the dominant factor influencing axial stiffness

(E_{11}), demonstrating that the models accurately capture the relationship between fiber content and material stiffness. Furthermore, the models' ability to identify matrix and fiber Poisson's ratios as the primary controllers of ν_{12} highlights their capacity to distinguish between the effects of different material properties on the material's behavior. Additionally, the matrix shear modulus being identified as the dictator of G_{12} underscores the ability of the models to accurately capture the complex relationships between material properties. These findings validate the models' ability to fit the data and demonstrate their capacity to capture structure-property relationships of significant engineering importance, thereby lending credibility to their predictions and recommendations.

Table 9. Sensitivity Index of E, N, and G

Mechanical Property	Feature	Sensitivity Index
E	Fiber Volume Fraction	0.67
	Fiber Orientation	0.21
	Matrix Stiffness	0.12
N	Matrix Poisson's Ratio	0.53
	Fiber Poisson's Ratio	0.33
	Fiber-Matrix Interaction	0.14
G	Matrix Shear Modulus	0.59
	Fiber Orientation	0.28
	Matrix Volume Fraction	0.13

The ML predictions exhibited significantly superior accuracy compared to analytical models such as the Rule of Mixtures and Chamis equations, particularly in capturing transverse and shear behavior (Table 10 in Appendix). Traditional approaches consistently and systematically overestimated stiffness and underestimated Poisson's ratio, highlighting their reliance on simplifying assumptions. In contrast, ML models demonstrated a close agreement with Digimat simulations, with deviations typically below 3% for E_{11} and 5% for G_{12} . This underscores their potential as computationally efficient surrogates for high-fidelity simulation tools.

Robustness analysis provided conclusive evidence of the benefits of ensemble approaches. The results showed that under $\pm 10\%$ perturbations in input features, boosting models consistently produced narrow confidence intervals and stable predictions, demonstrating a marked resilience. In contrast, simpler models displayed greater sensitivity and variability, underscoring the reliability of advanced machine learning techniques in unavoidable input uncertainty scenarios.

Taken together, the findings indicate that machine learning offers both predictive accuracy and interpretability for composite material systems. By identifying key microstructural drivers and achieving strong agreement with established simulations, the models demonstrate potential not only as predictive tools but also as design aids for optimizing glass fiber-reinforced polymers.

Conclusion

In this study, the effectiveness of ML models in predicting the mechanical properties of composite materials. The results indicated that ML algorithms, particularly ensemble methods, provided highly accurate predictions and demonstrated robust generalization. The key findings of this work can be summarized as follows:

- Simpler machine learning models, such as k-NN and SVR, were outperformed by more complex ensemble models, such as CatBoost, XGBoost, and Gradient Boosting, in dealing with intricate, non-linear relationships within the data.
- Features such as fiber volume fraction, matrix Poisson's ratio, and shear modulus were found to be the most significant factors, highlighting their importance in accurately predicting material properties.
- The analysis showed significant positive relationships between fibre friction and the axial Young's modulus (E_{11}), and between the resin Poisson's ratio and Poisson's ratio (ν_{12}), which underscored their influence on composite material behavior.
- The ML models demonstrated good consistency with Digimat outputs, with discrepancies of less than 3% for E_{11} and 5% for G_{12} , confirming the reliability of the ML method.
- Robust predictive modeling benefits from ML models that automatically give precedence to substantial features, yielding valuable information about material properties and further underscoring the significance of feature prioritization.
- Simpler models struggle to account for the complex feature interactions inherent in the behavior of composite materials, emphasizing the need for more advanced algorithms for accurate predictions.
- The findings suggest that machine learning holds considerable potential for optimizing composite material properties through improved prediction accuracy and better understanding of material behavior.

Despite the promising outcomes, the study has some limitations, such as the relatively small dataset, which may limit the models' generalizability to other material systems or manufacturing processes. The complexity of nonlinear interactions between features was another challenge that could be better addressed with more advanced hybrid models or deep feature engineering techniques. Further validation with larger and more diverse datasets, along with an exploration of hybrid models combining ML with traditional methods, would be beneficial. Future research should also focus on expanding the scope of the analyzed material systems, including different fiber architectures and hybrid composites, to enhance the model's performance and applicability.

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Appendix

Figure 3. Graphical Presentation of the Performance of ML Models for Young Modulus (E)
(a) Random Forest, (b) Gradient Boosting, (c) XGBoost, (d) CatBoost, (e) K-NN, (f) Elastic Net, (g) linear regression, (h) decision tree, (i) SVR, (j) AdaBoost, (k) ensemble

Figure 4. Graphical Presentation of the Performance of ML Models for Poisson's Ratio (ν_{12}) (a) random forest, (b) Gradient Boosting, (c) XGBoost, (d) CatBoost, (e) K-NN, (f) Elastic Net, (g) linear regression, (h) decision tree, (i) SVR, (j) AdaBoost, and (k) ensemble

Figure 5. Graphical Presentation of the Performance of Machine Learning Models for In-Plane Shear Modulus (G) (a) Random Forest, (b) Gradient Boosting, (c) XGBoost, (d) CatBoost, (e) K-NN, (f) Elastic Net, (g) Linear Regression, (h) decision tree, (i) SVR, (j) AdaBoost, and (k) ensemble.

Table 10. Comparison Table between the Digimat/ML Results and the Predictions from the Rule of Mixtures (ROM), Chamis Model, and Bridging model for 8 Composite Configurations

S#	E ₁₁ (Digimat)	ROME ₁₁	ChamisE ₁₁	v ₁₂ (Digimat)	ROM v ₁₂	Chamis v ₁₂	G ₁₂ (Digimat)	ROMG ₁₂	ChamisG ₁₂	BridgingG ₁₂
1	20482.0	43944.5	43944.5	0.5347	0.33	0.33	1710.7	0.76	0.68	4684.05
2	16740.0	44887.5	44887.5	0.3995	0.33	0.33	1656.7	0.34	0.31	6438.88
3	35482.0	43805.0	43805.0	0.4226	0.33	0.33	1755.8	0.82	0.74	4464.08
4	31965.0	41582.5	41582.5	0.3652	0.26	0.26	2852.7	0.76	0.68	7613.42
5	7717.6	42027.0	42027.0	0.2945	0.26	0.26	1346.5	0.20	0.18	5612.92
6	26672.0	44119.5	44119.5	0.3624	0.33	0.33	1521.3	0.60	0.54	4692.14
7	40709.0	50620.0	50620.0	0.2957	0.25	0.25	2803.5	0.98	0.88	5807.15
8	34374.0	46325.5	46325.5	0.3179	0.29	0.29	2581.6	0.74	0.67	6907.33